

Management

**PERCEPTION OF PEOPLE ON AADHAAR (LINKAGE, USAGE &
VOTING) A CASE STUDY (2014-16) WITH REFERENCE TO CHITTOOR
DISTRICT AP, INDIA**

Dr. K V V Raaju^{*1}

^{*1} Senior Assistant Professor, Madanpalli Institute of Technology and Sciences, Madanpalli,
Chittoor District, AP, India

UGC Sponsored Minor Research Project Proposal 829

Abstract

This article is a survey done to know how the people linked their aadhaar number to the voter id, gas cylinder, fee reimbursement, Bank account, House & Water tax, Birth Certificate, Admission in a School, RTO license, Raitu Runa Mafi, Employer data, Income/Caste/ Nativity. This article also collected the information on how is the usage of aadhaar as a proof of identity and the people voting on continue the aadhaar and linking of aadhaar.

Keywords: Aadhaar; Unique Identification Number; Enrollment; Perception.

Cite This Article: Dr. K V V Raaju. (2017). “PERCEPTION OF PEOPLE ON AADHAAR (LINKAGE, USAGE & VOTING) A CASE STUDY (2014-16) WITH REFERENCE TO CHITTOOR DISTRICT AP, INDIA.” *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 5(7), 450-460. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.838647>.

1. Introduction

The Unique Identification Number aadhaar card is a prestigious project introduced by Central Government. The objective of aadhaar is to link all the people of India. From the starting point of its implementing and now the total money spent on this project is 5630 cores. Totally 78.65 cores aadhaar numbers are allotted. This information given by the parliament on May 13th 2015. The total amount approved for the project for the year 2009-2017 is 13,633.22 crores (source Economic times March, 2013).¹ Linking of aadhaar numbers is restricted by the supreme court to LPG subsidy and for public distribution system. The court has not allowed the Banking, Telecom, and other few sectors have not been linked with aadhaar card. Public are aware of this information. There is a criticism on aadhaar that issue of aadhaar numbers may disturb the right to individuality as per article 21. The final judgment is not yet delivered by the Supreme Court yet.

But the Government is linking it still to several programs like Voter Id, Pensions, RTO, Scholarships, Gas cylinders, Fee Reimbursements, Bank accounts, School Admissions, Death, Birth certificates, Employment details with Employer data, Caste, income and residential certificates . Government now is linking the aadhaar card with all fields. And here it is the situation it is right time to know the people’s perception.

2. Aadhaar Enrolment in Chittoor District AP

There are three divisions in Chittoor 1. Chittoor division 2. Tirupathi division 3. Madanapalle division. Chittoor district consists of 23 mandals and Tirupathi 16 and Madanapalle 34 mandals totally 73 mandals. In almost all the mandals the enrolment is more than 100%. In most of the places the enrolment is more than the populations.²

Total 161 E seva Authorized agents worked on enrolments of aadhaar. The total enrolment of aadhaar done through 2 phases. The total process done through watching the progress reports. Totally 40, 24,427 people enrolled out of 41, 22,456 (97.62 percent)³

Chittoor district is located in Andhra Pradesh. The place where it is called as Rayalaseema region. Chittoor District is having three divisions called Chittoor, Tirupathi and Madanapalle. The aadhaar is issued the number is for life. Every institutions whether it is private, Government or educational are linked with aadhaar. Aadhaar for niraadhaar. A survey planned with a sample of 400 at 95% confidence level. In that 50 people opinion analyzed and we got the following results.

Table 1: Showing Percentage of Linking Aadhaar to Voter ID

S.No.	Voter Id	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	9	18	18	18
2	Yes	41	82	82	100
	Total	50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 1 shows the linkage of aadhaar number to voter Id. Out of 50, 41 people (82%) linked with and 9 (18%) not linked.

Table 2: Showing Percentage of linking Aadhaar to Gas Cylinder

S.No.	Gas Cylinder	frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	20	40	40	40
2	Yes	30	60	60	100
3	Total	50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 2 shows the linkage of aadhaar number to gas cylinder. Out of 50, 30 people (60%) linked with and 20 (40%) not linked.

Table 3: Showing Percentage of Aadhaar to linking for Fee Reimbursement

S.No.	Fee Reimbursement	frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	27	54	54	54
2	Yes	23	46	46	100
3	Total	50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 3 shows out of 50, 23 people (46%) linked Bank account with aadhaar and 27 (54%) not linked.

Table 4: showing Percentage of Aadhaar linking to Bank Account

S.No.	Bank Account	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	7	14	14	14
2	Yes	43	86	86	100
3	Total	50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 4 shows the linkage of aadhaar to bank account. Out of 50, 43(86%) linked and 7(14%) not linked.

Table 5: Showing percentage of aadhaar linking to house & water tax.

Sino	House & Water tax	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	39	78	78	78
2	Yes	11	22	22	100
	Total	50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 5 shows linkage of aadhaar to house & water tax, Out of 50, 39(78%) not linked and 11 (22%) linked.

Table 6: Showing Percentage of Aadhaar linking to Birth Certificate

S.No.	Birth Certificate	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	28	56	56	56
2	Yes	22	44	44	100
3	Total	50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 6 shows that for birth certificate 28(56%) not linked and 22(44%) linked.

Table 7: Showing Percentage of Aadhaar linking to Admission in a School

S.No.	Admission in a School	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	35	70	70	70
2	Yes	15	30	30	100
3	Total	50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 7 shows that for admission in a school 35 (70%) not linked and 15(30%) linked.

Table 8: Showing Percentage of Aadhaar linking to RTO license

S.No.	RTO License	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	29	58	58	58
2	Yes	21	42	42	100
3	Total	50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 8 shows that for Rto license 29(58%) not linked and 21(42%) linked.

Table 9: Showing Percentage of Aadhaar linking to AP Raitu Rune Mafia (agricultural loan)

S.No.	AP Raito Rune Mafia (agriculture loan)	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	44	88	88	88
2	Yes	6	12	12	100
		50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 9 shows linking to ratio rune mafia 44(88%) not linked and 6 (12%) linked

Table 10: Showing the Percentage of Aadhaar linking to Employer data

S.No.	Employer Data	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	32	64	64	64
2	Yes	18	36	36	100
	Total	50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 10 shows that linking aadhaar to employer data 32(64%) not linked and 18(36%) linked

Table 11: Showing the percentage of linking Aadhaar to Income/Caste/Nativity

S.No.	Income/Caste/Nativity	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	No	12	24	24	24
2	Yes	38	76	76	100
	Total	50	100	100	

(Source: Field Survey)

Table 11 shows that linking of aadhaar to caste income nativity 12(24%) not linked and 38(76%) linked.

Total Linked and Unlinked With Percentages

Linking of aadhaar to voter id, gas cylinder, etc.,

S.No.	Item	Linked	Percentage	Unlinked	Percentage
1	Bank account	43	86	14	7
2	Voter Id	41	82	9	18
3	Income/Caste/Nativity	38	76	12	24
4	Gas cylinder	30	60	20	40
5	Fee Reimbursement	23	46	27	54
6	Birth Certificate	22	44	28	56
7	RTO	21	42	29	58
8	Employer Data	18	36	32	64
9	Admission in a school	15	30	35	70
10	House & Water tax	11	22	39	78
11	Ap raitu runa mafi (agri)	6	12	44	88
	Total	268		289	

It is found that still linkage is not yet fully completed and in some areas it is high and in some areas it is less. 1st place occupied by bank account, followed by voter id, followed by income/caste/nativity, followed by gas cylinder, followed by fee reimbursement, followed by birth certificate, followed by RTO, followed by employer data, followed by admission in a school, followed by house and water tax and agriculture loan. We can say that linkage of aadhaar to be improved.

Table 12: How many time Aadhaar used as proof of Identity

S.No.	Times	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	10 times	6	12	12	12
2	2 times	7	14	14	26
3	5 times	20	40	40	66
4	above 10 times	17	34	34	100
5	Total	50	100	100	

Table 12 shows the usage of aadhaar by the people out of 50 Majority 20 used 5 times(40%), followed by 17 used above 10 times(34%), followed by 7 used 2 times(14%), followed by 6 used 10 times(12%). We can understand that usage of aadhaar is day by day going in an increasing trend.

Table 13: Which one is used as proof of Identity & Address by your choice?

S.No.	Item	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	Aadhaar Card	36	72	72	72
2	Driving License	3	6	6	78
3	Pan Card	2	4	4	82
4	Ration Card	6	12	12	94
5	Voter Id	3	6	6	100
	Total	50	100	100	

Table 13 shows the choices of Proof of Identity of their choices. Out of 50 Majority 36 chosen aadhaar as proof of Identity (72%), followed by 6 with ration card (12%), followed by 3 driving license and voter identity, followed by 2 pan card (4%). With this analysis also we can say that usage of aadhaar is high.

Table 14: As per your wish and will do you want that giving Aadhaar numbers to people and linking it to be continued or stop or can't say vote it.

S.No.	Item	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative
1	Can't Say	12	24	24	24
2	Continue	38	76	76	100
3	Stop	0	0	0	
	Total	50	100	100	

Table 14 shows the voting results of the people. Out of 50, 38 people majority voting to continue the aadhaar enrolment and linking of aadhaar and 12 people voted against it and willing to stop.

3. Summary & Conclusion

We can say with the above analysis the linkage, usage of aadhaar is day by day improving and increasing. The majority people accepting the aadhaar and linkage of aadhaar to several government amenities.

References

- [1] <http://economictimes.indiatimes.com/topic/Aadhaar>
- [2] Right to Information Act letter dated 14/08/2014. Reply on 18/08/14
- [3] Reply for the letter dated 14/08/2014. Reply on 18/08/14 RTI
- [4] <http://uidai.gov.in/>
- [5] <http://uidai.gov.in/aapka-aadhaar.html>
- [6] <http://uidai.gov.in/what-is-aadhaar.html>
- [7] <http://www.dhanbank.com/pdf/ploan-documentation.pdf>
- [8] <http://uidai.gov.in/all-about-uidai/mandates-objective.html>
- [9] <http://uidai.gov.in/all-about-uidai/vision,core-values-mission-statement.html>
- [10] <http://uidai.gov.in/all-about-uidai/mandates-objective.html>

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: raju8187@ gmail.com